

Isometric and bacilliform particles of rice tungro virus complex.

The presumed tungro complex particles were isometric and bacilliform (see figure). The isometric particles were 27-28 nm in diameter when negatively stained in 2% uranyl acetate (UA) and 30 nm in diameter in 1% neutral sodium phosphotungstate (PTA). The bacilliform particles were 23 nm in diameter in UA and 31-33 nm in diameter in PTA. The length of the bacilliform particles was variable in both stains. Apparently undamaged particles with both ends rounded were 110-190 nm long in UA, although no particular modal length was detected.

Hibino and associates reported in *Phytopathology* 68:1412, 1978, on the negatively stained appearance and dimensions of particles of the tungro complex. They used PTA only on crude preparations. Our results in PTA confirm their measurements of particles in the same stain. However, we note that the bacilliform particles particularly appeared damaged in our PTA preparations. We think that the substantially greater diameter compared to that in UA was due to artifactual swelling or flattening. ■

second. When nonviruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of both species, none of the progeny became infective.

These results indicate that *N. virescens* is also a vector of RDV, transmitting the virus in a persistent manner with transovarial passage. ■

Survey of rice diseases in the Vietnamese Mekong delta from 1978 to 1980

Pham van Kim, Nguyen thi Nghiem, Lam Len, and Dang ngoc Kinh, Plant Protection Department (PPD), University of Can Tho, Vietnam

Rice diseases in the Vietnamese Mekong delta were surveyed from 1978 to 1980, with 69 cooperators of the PPD, faculty of Agriculture, University of Can Tho. The results showed 25 diseases in rice fields and 6 fungi on stored grain. Blast, sheath blight, bacterial blight, and ufra were the most important diseases (see table).

Blast and sheath blight appeared everywhere in the delta, but were most severe in three regions.

Blast was severe in Tiengiang region and the southern part of Haugiang region (Fig. 1). In Tiengiang, blast was important in January, February, March, and July, with highest peaks in January and July every year. Node blast occurred in March.

In the southern part of Haugiang province, node blast was common in December-January, and leaf blast, in July. An epidemic of leaf blast in July 1978 destroyed more than 300 ha of seedling nurseries in the main season crop.

Severe sheath blight occurrence was observed in two regions — the northwestern region of the delta encompassing the whole of Angiang province and the northern part of Haugiang province, and in Tiengiang regions (Fig. 2).

Bacterial blight and ufra diseases were important in the rainy season and in deepwater areas. They sometimes caused severe losses in some limited areas.

Kernel smut broke out from February to April 1979 as an epidemic in the northwestern part of the delta. More

A new insect vector of rice dwarf virus

Xie Lian-hui, Lin Ji-ying, and Guo Jing-rong. Fujian College of Agriculture, Shaxian, China

Rice dwarf virus (RDV) is transmitted in a persistent manner with transovarial passage by *Nephotettix cincticeps*, *N. nigropictus*, and *Recilia dorsalis*.

N. virescens and *N. cincticeps* were collected 1974-1977 from rice fields in Fujian. Infectivity was tested on variety Zhin Zhuai 11 at the 3-leaf stage. Of 988 *N. virescens* and 969 *N. cincticeps* tested, 4.3% and 4.9% of the insects, respectively, were capable of causing

RDV infection in rice plants, indicating that infective insects of both species exist under natural conditions.

After an acquisition feeding of 3-4 days and a latent period of about 9 days both species transmitted the RDV (see table). RDV was persistent in the insect vector.

There was transovarial passage of RDV in both species. When viruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of *N. virescens*, the progeny became infective at 8% for the first generation and 4% for the second. When viruliferous females were crossed with nonviruliferous males of *N. cincticeps*, the progeny became infective at 19% for the first generation and 12% for the

Transmission of rice dwarf virus by two species of *Nephotettix*, Shaxian, China.

Species	Insects tested (no.)	Infective insects (%)	Latent period (days)			
			In insect		In plant	
			Av	Range	Av	Range
<i>N. cincticeps</i>	544	35	9.4	6-32	10.6	7-48
<i>N. virescens</i>	567	31	9.0	7-21	12.4	8-38